

was less aggressive, and that Xiang-Zhou No. 5 may have specific resistance genes effective against ZC15.

The cultivars that have shown durable resistance in the field have partial resistance to the races tested in this study. ■

Analysis of rice blast (BI) pathogen virulence in Egypt

A. P. K. Reddy, IRRI-Egypt Project, RRTC Sakha, Kafr el Sheikh, Egypt

We evaluated the virulence of *Pyricularia oryzae* in B1-affected areas of the Nile Delta (governorates of Beheira, Dakhalia, Damietta, Gharbia, and Kafr el Sheikh) 1988-89 summer seasons.

Rice leaves and panicles with typical B1 lesions were collected from farmers' fields. Single lesions were placed in petri dishes with wet filter paper and incubated at 25°C until sporulation.

A group of conidia was aseptically transferred with a pointed capillary tube to rice leaf agar. For the purpose of this study, mass cultures from single lesions were considered equivalent to single conidial isolates. (Previous studies under the same test conditions had indicated that single conidial cultures derived from single lesions are of one race.)

In 1988, 10 commercial cultivars and 8 international differentials were tested against 35 isolates. In 1989, 8 commercial cultivars and international differentials were tested against 52 isolates.

Test plants grown in 40- × 20- × 10-cm plastic boxes in 10-cm rows, 5 cm apart were inoculated with aqueous spore

P. oryzae isolates virulent to commercial rice cultivars in Egypt 1988 and 1989.

Cultivar	Virulence ^a (%)	
	1988 (n=35)	1989 (n=52)
Giza 159	100	100
Giza 171	100	100
Giza 172	100	100
Reiho	100	100
Giza 175	3 ^b	2 ^a
Giza 181	0	0
GZ1368-5-4	0	nt
GZ2175-5-6	20	53
IR28	0	0
IR50	0	nt

^a (n) = number isolates tested. nt = not tested. ^b Intermediate reaction.

suspension (about 50,000/ml). Inoculated plants were left in a moist chamber for 48 h, then transferred to the greenhouse.

Disease was scored 10-15 d later.

B1 virulence on local cultivars Giza 159, Giza 171, Giza 172, and Reiho was 100% both years (see table). Virulence was zero on indica cultivars IR28, IR50, and Giza 181, and rare on Giza 175. Currently popular breeding line GZ2175-5-6 was affected by 20% of the isolates in 1988 and 53% in 1989 (see table).

This increase in virulence on GZ2175-5-6 is associated with an increase in area sown to this line, from 1,000 ha in 1988 to 10,000 ha in 1989. ■

Resistance to blast (BI) in Egyptian rice varieties

A. P. K. Reddy and A. O. Bastawisi, Rice Research and Training Centre, Sakha, Egypt

B1 is a major production constraint in Egypt. Resistance in a series of japonica varieties released in 1954-84 was short. A few indica breeding lines (IR28, IR1626-203 [Giza 181]) released in recent years retain resistance, but they have limited commercial acceptability and narrow genetic bases.

We evaluated 500 improved cultivars, breeding lines, and germplasm of diverse origin against the prevailing B1 pathogen races ID13 and IG1 in the Nile Delta.

Entries grown in the greenhouse were inoculated with two representative isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* 15 d after sowing (DAS). Temperature was maintained at 21-32°C and relative humidity at >90% for 9-11 h. Cultivars found to be resistant 45 DAS are listed in Table 1.

Fifteen varieties were evaluated against three representative virulent isolates from the rice-growing delta. Entries planted in single rows in nursery boxes were inoculated at 15 DAS with virulent isolates originating from Dakhalia, Kafr el Sheikh, and Gharbia governorates. After 48 h in the humid chamber, they were transferred to glasshouse benches. Disease was recorded 15 d later.

All tested IRRI varieties were resistant to the local B1 pathogen races (Table 2). Some of the varieties (IR50, Ratna,

Table 1. Reaction of selected rice genotypes to 2 representative *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates of Egypt.

Cultivar	Reaction to <i>P. oryzae</i> isolates	
	ID13 ^a	IG1 ^b
IRRI		
IR20	1	1
IR22	1	1
IR24	1	2
IR28	1	1
IR36	1	1
IR50	1	1
IR52	1	1
IR60	1	1
IR62	1	1
IR64	1	1
IR66	1	1
IR2003-P18-16	1	1
IR2153-338-3	1	1
IR19743-46-1	1	1
IR25571-31-1	1	1
Thailand		
RD7	1	1
RD9	1	1
RD10	1	1
RD21	1	1
RD25	1	1
S. Korea		
Iri 370	1	1
Milyang 23	2	1
Milyang24	2	1
Milyang 80	2	1
Milyang 85	2	1
Suweon 346	1	1
Japan		
BL 1	1	1
Kanto 1	1	2
Tsuyuuake	1	3
Torida 1	1	1
India		
Bala	1	1
Basmati 370	1	1
Cauvery	1	1
CO 43	1	1
Padma	2	4
Ratna	1	1
Rasi	1	1
Tella hamsa	1	1
USA		
Mars	1	1
Lemont	1	1
Mercury	1	1
Noritai	1	1
Egypt		
Agami	3	4
Giza 175	2	1
Giza 181	1	1
Giza2175-5-6	8	2
Yabani 15 (susceptible)	7	8
Giza 159 (susceptible)	8	8
Giza 172 (susceptible)	8	8
Reiho (susceptible)	8	8

^a Isolate from Sidisalem, on Giza on 2175-5-6. ^b Isolate from RRTC research farm Sakha, on Giza 172.

Cauvery) have a history of susceptibility in the tropics. IR36, Rasi, and a few

Table 2. Reaction pattern of 15 rice varieties to 3 *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates in Egypt.

Variety	Reaction to isolate			Mean	Reaction	
	Po 361 ^a	Po 359	Po GMI		Egypt	Phil/India
<i>Indica</i>						
Cauvery	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.3	R	S
Ratna	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
IR50	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
IR36	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	MR
IR28	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	MS
Giza 181	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	S
Rasi	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	R	R
<i>Japonica</i>						
Gz 159	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Gz 171	6.5	9.0	9.0	8.2	S	S
Gz 172	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Reiho	7.5	9.0	9.0	8.5	S	S
Shin 2	5.5	6.5	6.0	6.0	MS	S
Aichi Asahi	8.0	9.0	9.0	8.6	S	S
Kanto 51	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.3	R	S
Toride 1	1.0	1.5	1.0	1.1	R	R
Mean	3.5	4.1	4.0			
CV (1)	7.1					
CV (2)	6.0					
LSD Main plot at 0.05						
Isolates at 0.01						
Interaction LSD at	0.05	= 0.47				
	0.01	= 0.64				

^aAverage value of 2 replications. Po 361 from Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, Po 359 from Dakhalia governorate. Po GMI from Gharbia governorate

others that have shown more durable resistance in other rice-growing environ-

ments appear to be better donors of B1 resistance in Egypt. ■

Changes in rice leaf pigment due to tungro (RTV) infection

B. Srinivasulu and R. Jeyarajan, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

Chlorosis and orange yellow color in leaves are characteristic symptoms of RTV disease in rice. We investigated the effect of RTV infection on green pigment (chlorophyll), orange pigment (carotene), and yellow pigment (xanthophyll) at different stages of pathogenesis.

Fifteen-day-old seedlings of susceptible TN1 were inoculated with RTV by

releasing three viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* (Dist.) per seedling. Infected leaves were graded as 1/3 orange yellow, 2/3 orange yellow, or completely orange yellow. Chlorophyll content was extracted and estimated in 80% acetone. Carotene and xanthophyll were extracted with 95% ethanol and 85% methanol, respectively, and estimated colorimetrically.

Chlorophyll content of diseased leaves was reduced in proportion to the length of orange-yellow color on a leaf (see table). In leaves that had turned completely orange yellow, chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll were reduced by 90, 94, and 91%, respectively.

Effect of RTV on pigment of rice leaves. Coimbatore, India.

Leaf color	Chlorophyll a	Chlorophyll b	Total chlorophyll	Carotene	Xanthophyll
Completely orange yellow	0.234	0.078	0.312	ND*	ND
2/3 orange yellow	0.564	0.119	0.689	0.005	0.003
1/3 orange yellow	1.380	0.680	2.184	ND	ND
Healthy	2.300	1.370	3.672	0.003	0.002
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.26	0.110	0.190		

^a ND = not determined

A slight increase in carotene and xanthophyll content was found in diseased leaves. ■

Development of kresek symptoms on some rice varieties

Y. Suryadi, Plant Pathology Department, Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops, Subang 41256, West Java, Indonesia

Xanthomonas campestris pv. *oryzae* (Xco) can cause kresek symptoms on rice seedlings. Great variations have been found among strains of Xco in terms of their pathogenicity in the rice plant.

We induced kresek in the screenhouse using different strains of Xco on seven rice varieties. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with two replications, with rice varieties Pelita 1-1, Java 14, Gemar, Cisadane, Citanduy, TNI, and IR54 in the main plots and three isolates or strains of Xco in the subplots.

Roots of 21-d-old seedlings were washed, dip-inoculated for 15 min with 48-h-old bacterial suspension ($\pm 10^9$ cfu/ml), and seedlings transplanted in a wooden seedling box. Disease incidence was recorded 14 d after inoculation.

Symptom development varied (see table). Cisadane had the least disease symptoms with all three Xco strains, followed by Java 14, Pelita 1-1, and Gemar. Mean infection ranged from 9.7 to 44.3%. ■

Development of kresek symptoms on 7 rice varieties Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988.

Variety	Wilted plant ^a (%)			
	Si 8502	Si 8401	Si 8519	Mean
Gemar	16.55	12.68	17.83	15.67 ab
Cisadane	9.26	11.93	7.97	9.72 a
Citanduy	26.75	21.65	20.72	23.04 bc
Pelita 1-1	14.56	19.94	11.95	15.48 ab
IR54	36.99	33.85	22.62	31.15 c
Java 14	14.31	16.06	16.05	15.47 ab
TNI	51.09	48.74	32.94	44.26 d
Mean	24.21 a	23.55 a	18.58 b	-

CV variety (%) = 33.28
CV isolates (%) = 17.73

^a Isolates Si 8502, Si 8401, and Si 8519 represented Indonesian bacterium groups III, V, and VI, respectively. Means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05).